

Electrochemical Behaviour of some Selected Ketoacid Oximes and Semicarbazones

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Manuscript received 16 November 1990, revised 2 September 1991, accepted 7 November 1991

THE electrochemical reductions of azomethine compounds especially reductions of aliphatic oximes and semicarbazones have been quite extensively investigated¹. However electrochemical investigations of aliphatic ketoacid oximes and semicarbazones have not yet been studied to the best of our knowledge.

The purpose of this work is to study the electrochemical reduction behaviour of pyruvic acid oxime, pyruvic acid semicarbazone and 2-oxoglutaric acid semicarbazone by using different electrochemical techniques.

Experimental

The details of the equipment used for the different electroreduction techniques mentioned have been described elsewhere². The dropping mercury electrode (DME) used had the following characteristics: flow rate, 2.73 mg s⁻¹; area, 0.0223 cm²; drop time, 3 s and hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) area, 0.0328 cm².

Pyruvic acid oxime³, pyruvic acid semicarbazone⁴ and 2-oxoglutaric acid semicarbazone⁴ were prepared from the corresponding ketoacids according to the literature. HClO₄ (1 M), HCl (1 M) and the universal buffers (pH 2.0–12.0) were used as supporting electrolytes. All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

Results and Discussion

All the three compounds are found to give a single well-defined wave/peak (Fig. 1) in acidic solutions (pH ≤ 4) corresponding to the reduction of protonated azomethine group (C=N-)H⁺, to the corresponding amino group respectively with an

Fig. 1. Typical d.c. polarogram of pyruvic acid oxime in 1M HClO₄; concn.=0.5 mM, drop time=3 s.

uptake of four electrons per molecule. In neutral media (pH ≤ 6), the wave/peak is observed to be merging with hydrogen evolution whereas in basic media (pH ≥ 8), no reduction is observed.

The diffusion-controlled and adsorption free nature of the electrode process for all the three compounds investigated is evidenced from the linear plots of *i*_a vs *h*^{1/2} (Fig. 2) and *i*_p vs *v*^{1/2} passing

Fig 2. *I*_a vs *h*^{1/2} plots of pyruvic acid semicarbazone in (a) 1M HClO₄, (b) 1M HCl, (c) pH 2.0 and (d) pH 4.0; concn.=0.5 mM.

through origin. In cyclic voltammetry, the current function *i*_p/C*v*^{1/2} is observed to be fairly constant with the scan rate (*v*) indicating the electrode process to be free from kinetic complications. The irreversibility of the electrode process is verified by logarithmic analysis of the wave. The slope of the *E* vs log *i*/(*i*_a - *i*) graph exceeds appe-

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ciably 59.15/n mV and the numerical value of $E_{1/4} - E_{3/4}$ exceeds 56.4/n mV (Ref. 5).

The $E_{1/2}$ and E_p values of all three compounds are found to be pH-dependent and shift towards negative values with increase in pH of the buffer systems indicating the proton involvement in the electrode process. Possibly an increase in pH increases the dissociation constant of the protonated species and these factors affect the protonation rate, consequently the $E_{1/2}$ and E_p values are shifted to more negative values. Such a situation occurs when protonation precedes electrons transfer⁶.

When compared to the ketoacid semicarbazones, keto acid oximes are found to be reduced more easily because of the polar nature of the N→O bond. In 2-oxoglutaric acid semicarbazone, the presence of CH₂CH₂COOH group adjacent to the azomethine group increases the electronic charge on the azomethine group compared to the CH₃ group present in pyruvic acid semicarbazone, rendering the reduction process to be difficult in the former compound. From the comparison of the half-wave potentials of the above three compounds the ease of reduction is observed to follow the order: pyruvic acid oxime > pyruvic acid semicarbazone > 2-oxoglutaric acid semicarbazone.

Millicoulometry⁷ is employed in 1 M HClO₄ and pH 2.0 to find out the number of electrons involved in the electrode process and the results showed the *n*-value to be 4 in both the supporting electrolytes for all the three compounds. Controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) experiments also confirmed the above results. CPE experiments were carried out for pyruvic acid oxime (-0.60 V vs SCE), pyruvic acid semicarbazone (-0.70 V vs SCE) and 2-oxoglutaric acid semicarbazone (-0.75 V vs SCE) in 1 M HClO₄ and the isolated amino products after CPE experiments are confirmed as alanine (nujol, 3 050, 1 600 cm⁻¹), alanine (3 020, 1 620 cm⁻¹)

and glutamic acid (3 000, 1 650 cm⁻¹) respectively by ir spectral studies.

The kinetic parameters of the electrode process such as diffusion coefficient (*D*) and heterogeneous forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) values calculated from d.c. polarography and cyclic voltammetric techniques for the three compounds are reported in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The diffusion current (*i_d*) and peak currents (*i_p*) for the three compounds are found to decrease with increase in pH of the buffer solution and this may be attributed to the less availability of protons with increase in pH. Hence the diffusion coefficient values also vary in the same manner. As expected, a general increase in *D* values are noticed with decrease in molecular weight of the species under investigation. For instance, under similar experimental conditions, diffusion current values and hence the *D* values obtained for pyruvic acid oxime are found to be higher than that of the other two species due to the lower molecular weight in both the techniques employed. The *D* values for the reduction of azomethine group in the three compounds are found to be in the order of 10⁻⁶ cm² s⁻¹ and are observed to be in good agreement in both the techniques indicating the adsorption-free nature of the electrode process. D.C. polarographic *D* values may be considered as more reliable than cyclic voltammetric *D* values because of the fresh and renewal nature of the DME in the former technique. The forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) values for the reduction of azomethine group are found to be very high in acidic media in both the techniques employed, since the reduction of azomethine group is facile because of its protonated form. With increase in pH of the solution the $k_{f,h}^0$ values obtained from both the techniques are in general found to decrease and this may be attributed to the shift of $E_{1/2}$ and E_p values to more negative values with increase in pH. This trend shows that the electrode reaction tends to become more irreversible

TABLE 1—TYPICAL D.C. POLAROGRAPHIC DATA

Concn. = 0.5 mM, Drop time = 3 s

Supporting electrolyte	Pyruvic acid oxime				Pyruvic acid semicarbazone				2-Oxoglutaric acid semicarbazone			
	$-E_{1/2}$ V	<i>i_d</i> μA	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹	$-E_{1/2}$ V	<i>i_d</i> μA	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹	$-E_{1/2}$ V	<i>i_d</i> μA	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹
1 M HClO ₄	0.49	8.50	7.33	3.06×10^{-10}	0.60	6.60	5.42	6.79×10^{-13}	0.64	5.75	4.01	7.65×10^{-13}
1 M HCl	0.50	8.40	7.15	7.39×10^{-11}	0.61	6.55	5.35	4.30×10^{-13}	0.64	5.60	3.96	6.15×10^{-13}
pH 2.0	0.63	8.20	6.82	5.50×10^{-13}	0.73	6.00	4.65	4.65×10^{-13}	0.78	5.10	3.64	9.38×10^{-13}
pH 4.0	0.87	7.45	5.55	2.55×10^{-13}	0.92	5.80	4.31	2.79×10^{-13}	1.03	4.95	3.14	1.13×10^{-13}

TABLE 2—TYPICAL CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA

Concn. = 0.5 mM, Scan rate = 40 mV s⁻¹

Supporting electrolyte	Pyruvic acid oxime				Pyruvic acid semicarbazone				2-Oxoglutaric acid semicarbazone			
	$-E_p$ V	<i>i_p</i> μA	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹	$-E_p$ V	<i>i_p</i> μA	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹	$-E_p$ V	<i>i_p</i> μA	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹
1 M HClO ₄	0.50	8.20	7.91	1.03×10^{-10}	0.62	6.75	5.95	4.45×10^{-13}	0.67	5.85	4.10	1.50×10^{-13}
1 M HCl	0.51	8.15	7.33	6.20×10^{-11}	0.615	6.60	5.65	3.04×10^{-13}	0.68	5.70	3.99	7.25×10^{-14}
pH 2.0	0.63	7.90	6.70	1.63×10^{-13}	0.74	5.95	4.94	4.55×10^{-13}	0.82	5.20	3.85	1.30×10^{-13}
pH 4.0	0.88	7.20	5.96	1.62×10^{-13}	1.01	5.70	4.69	7.53×10^{-13}	1.07	4.85	3.27	1.82×10^{-13}

with increase in pH⁸. The $k_{f,h}^0$ values obtained from both the techniques show that the reduction is more difficult in 2-oxoglutaric acid semicarbazone and the order of ease of reduction is noticed to be similar to that obtained from the $E_{1/2}$ data.

Based on the results obtained, the reduction mechanism proposed for the three compounds is presented in Scheme 1.

In the acidic solutions of pH ≤ 4 :

(a) Pyruvic acid oxime

(b) Pyruvic acid semicarbazone

(c) 2-Oxoglutaric acid semicarbazone

Scheme 1

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (C.S.R.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing financial assistance.

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